

Advertising Pragmatics of Contemporary Media for Polylingualism and Polyculturalism

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ABSTRACT: The article considers advertising pragmatics of contemporary media for polylingualism and polyculturalism as the urgent need for advertising information about different types of goods has become a prerequisite for the development and dissemination of a hybrid type of text – advertising text, announcement of things or services. The research aims at the functional specifics of advertising texts in polycultural and polylingual contexts, among which is a variety of publications and outdoor advertising. To achieve the objective, it is important to consider the goals (set tasks) associated with the research questions. They are: (i) to outline the presentation patterns of trademarks and define the essence of the advertising text in the poly-lingual context, (ii) to determine the pragmatic direction of advertising texts of modern media, accounting for the discursive-functional aspects, (iii) to trace manifestation of multiculturalism and/or polyculturalism and polylingualism of the advertising text as a non-standard type of text. It is stated advertising slogan is a communicative message that has a pragmatic instruction to convey true information about the subject of advertising to the largest number of people in order to encourage them to take action - to use and purchase the advertised product. The slogan is focused primarily on achieving the maximum pragmatic effect: to present the brand, distribute the advertised products, actually sell the product, and even forcibly impose it on a potential consumer. It is found the following aspects are clearly combined, which logically represent the advertising text as a non-standard object of linguistic description in the polylingual cultures: 1) polylingual components: introduction into the advertising message of linguistic facts by different types of fonts, a combination of natural and unnatural semiotic systems (signs, drawings, symbols), introduction to the text of visuals; 2) multicultural and/or polycultural components.

KEYWORDS- advertising text, mass media, polyculturalism, multiculturalism, polylingualis, advertisement (ads), advertisement stylistic properties

INTRODUCTION

Advertising is a developmental field of activity, the rules of which developers of this social sector, and especially marketers, are clearly establishing. As Katerniuk (2006) notes advertising is not only the engine of trade, but also an incentive for the development of material activities. Advertising embodies everywhere – in trade, the political and cultural life of the society, the use of various semiotic systems, and the linguistic signs of all languages, in particular. This indirectly affects the internal development of society and civilizational processes in the era of globalization, where polyculturalism and polylingualism play their significant roles.

The urgent need for advertising information about different types of goods has become a prerequisite for the development and dissemination of a hybrid type of text – advertising text, announcement of things or services. Announcement means advertising information about the content of a newspaper or magazine issue or TV, radio programs. It is necessary to differentiate between announcement and summary, or synopsis, which stands for a short advertising text about a book or movie. The result will be a special discursive plane of texts, which was established with the rise and spread of the advertising market of goods.

It is stated that the constant appeal of scientists from different fields of knowledge to the issues of advertising is determined by the expediency of describing certain socially significant problems of the contemporary time, among which the issues of formation and education in the field of culture are important. In addition, the relevance of the topic is due to the active development of marketing linguistics (Kawecki, 2011; Lukin, 2015; Kostiushkina, 2016; Sabitova, 2020), the need to systematize and describe structural-semantic, functional, communicative-discursive, and pragmatic features of advertising texts, common in modern discursive practices in the general context of polyculturalism and polylingualism of the modern consumer.

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The purpose of the research is to consider the functional specifics of advertising texts in poly-cultural and poly-lingual contexts, among which is a variety of publications and outdoor advertising. To achieve the objective, it is important to consider the following goals (tasks as set) associated with the research questions:

- 1) To outline the presentation patterns of trademarks and define the essence of the advertising text in the poly-lingual context,
- 2) To determine the pragmatic direction of advertising texts of modern media, accounting for the discursive-functional aspects,
- 3) To trace manifestation of multiculturalism and/or polyculturalism and polylingualism of the advertising text as a non-standard type of text.

METHODOLOGY AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Methodology

The methods and techniques used in the research process were chosen in accordance with the goals and stages of the work. In particular, they are:

- Analysis of scientific literature, used to describe the theoretical framework of the advertising research as one of the modern discursive practices and issues of multicultural communication in a variety of languages,
- Synthesis, used in general theoretical and applied aspects,
- Descriptive method, applied for (i) separation of language units in the aspect of the research topic, (ii) clarification of pragmatics of advertising texts in the aspect of polyculturalism and polylingualism,
- Comparative method, for the ratio of textual and visual components of advertising text.

The sources of factual material were advertising texts published in the Ukrainian publications from the beginning of the XXI century. The material for the study were printed texts of advertising on Ukrainian and foreign TV channels, in Internet publications and visual advertising, etc. The selected Ukrainian channels were market-leading media such as *1 + 1*, *Inter*, and *STB*. The foreign channels were inter alia *BBC News*, *CNBC*, *Euronews*, *Bloomberg Television*. The main language for the research study was Ukrainian and translations into English, German, Portuguese, and Russian.

Literature review

Modern linguistics considers the text in different aspects.

Zahnitko (2012) as one of the most distinguished Slavonic scholars defines the text as follows. First, text in the English, Ukrainian and other languages originate from Latin textus 'fabric, plexus, connection'. Second, its first definition connects to a number of entries:

- (i) A holistic semiotic form of psycho-speech-thinking human activity, conceptually and structurally organized, dialogically embedded in the interiorized being, the semiotic universe of ethnos or civilization, which is pragmatically directed to communication;
- (ii) The result of communication, its structural and linguistic component and simultaneous implementation;
- (iii) The structure, in which the discourse is embodied after its completion;
- (iv) Oral or written work of the language-making process, logically complete, composed of a number of special linguistic expressions, united by different types of lexical, grammatical, logical, stylistic connections, which has the appropriate orientation and pragmatic guidance [31, p. 16-17].

In the general semiotic sense, Lotman (2002) sees the text as any organized set of signs that unfolds in time and space [15]. Such semiotic signs, in opinion of Zahnitko (2006), include, for example, custom as a text, culture as a text, dance as a text and so on. It is assumed such an approach much broadens the horizons of polyculturalism in the polylingual contexts. Further, the scholar underlines that from the point of view of discourse, the text is understood as a written fixation of a discourse or other work of speech. Zahnitko (ibid.) adds that text is seen as an element of the expanded (external) base of language consciousness [31, p. 16-17].

Having defined what is meant by the text as an umbrella term, it is important to move to the advertising text, or advertisement, or an ad.

Thus, it is agreed that advertising text stands for an element of advertising communication, which is a direct carrier of information and emotional impact of the communicator on the recipient of the message. The advertising text has a specific form and reaches the recipient through a specific communication channel [31, p. 20].

Advertising is most common in modern media or visualization. It may manifest with the help of posters, billboards, banners, etc., and aims to have a real impact on its consumer - either real, or virtual, or potential.

Such mechanisms as explained by Bogatova (2015) and connected with pragmatics of advertising texts are primarily due to the fact that media discourse as a kind of functional discourses "constitutes social reality, attributing meaning to both social and physical objects; discourse is not a reflection of social relations, it itself constitutes a system of social relations" [3, p. 104]. The pragmatic dominant of the advertising text together with the social dominant is one of the most important discursive categories. To support

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the statement, Kormilitsyna and Sirotinina (2015) note, “Any text conveys information, but it is not in any that it is socially significant; however, in the media it is a prerequisite for its dissemination” [14, p. 8].

Kara-Murza (2011) agrees that advertising is an integral part of the media, concentrating on their goals: to give us such signs that we, by embedding these signs in the context, change the image of this context in our perception. The author suggests such connections of the text or deed with reality imposes certain interpretation that our perception of reality becomes distorted in the direction desired by the manipulator [9, p. 28].

To speak of advertising makes it necessary to look down the channels of its origin. Following Katerniuk (2006), the lexeme advertising came from the two Latin words: *reclamo* ‘exclamation’ and *reclamare* ‘respond’ [10, p. 52]. Starobinskiy (1996) in his textbook on *Self-Advertising* comments advertising is used in various forms, using different types of information about a natural or legal person, product or idea, which is addressed to a specific group of people and is designed to form, maintain interest in natural or legal person, product, idea, etc. [27, p. 23]. Romat (2000) considers advertising from the point of view of marketing and the researcher emphasizes, “Advertising is a dynamic, rapidly transforming sphere of human activity. ... The nature of advertising, its content and form undergo metamorphoses together with the development of the productive forces of society, the change of socio-economic formations” [21, p. 11]. Romat believes that the global factors of advertising “dialectics” are the needs of production, trade and finance, the form of government, the goals of various religious denominations, politicians and ordinary citizens. Moreover, it is stated that among other things, advertising is rightly defined as part of human culture, which develops according to its internal laws.

Somewhat different is the focus of Baranov (2013) to research advertising, where the key focus lies with linguistic examination of the text. Baranov notes that “advertising discourse actualizes various aspects of the plan of the content of the language sign - from the actual meaning to the presuppositions and internal form” [1, p. 383].

The Polish researchers (Szpunar, 2008; Tarsa, 2020) in the field of advertising look at the importance of visuals. According to Magdalena Szpunar, “modern man has evolved from homo sapiens to homo videns, a being who prefers an image, and what is shown is more important to her than what is spoken or written. (...) We live in a world where visual images with various goals and intended effects are in the lead, and a society becomes modern when one of its main activities is the production and consumption of images” [26, p. 105]. Jadwiga Tarsa (2020) notes that it is hard to disagree with the description of the functioning of modern society, which is guided by the principle that it is better to see once than to hear it twice. The image plays an increasingly important role in the human life. People are surrounded by colorful, bright photos of advertisements, majority of magazines mainly contain photos of various goods and products, and the text has been pushed to the background [28, p. 11].

However, there is more to that. It is agreed with Zahnitko (2012) that advertising texts are first of all texts of influence, as their main role is to function as “strong (energy-intensive) texts that resonate with the reader and generate new target texts” [31, p. 21]. In the contemporary world of polyculture and polylingual surroundings, with many new ideas and visions coming from everywhere around, it is next to impossible to live without advertising. Thus, Burmaka (2002) emphasizes advertising in modern society is gradually becoming part of national culture and even claims the status of a separate industry, which focuses on the mass consumer and in this case affects ideals and social attitudes [5, p. 13].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Advertising has become more and more versatile. No surprise why different researchers attempt to classify advertising, group it under classes, in attempt to determine the most productive ways of influence. To this end, Vikentiev (2020) and Golman (2002) analyze underlying features in the basis of advertising and distinguish the following types of advertising [30; 8]:

1) Information advertising - its main task is to convey to consumers information about goods, services, etc.
Persuasive, or comparative, advertising is a type of advertising, which compares the advertised product with the products made and marketed by competitors,

Reminder advertising – this kind of advertising aims to remind about the availability of the product in the market, and its characteristics,

4) Supportive advertising is designed to support consumers who bought the product, to assure them of the right choice
American marketers Moriarty, Mitchell and Wells (2019) propose a different classification of advertising, which includes the following varieties [17]:

(i) Vintage (branded) – this advertising is aimed at creating long-lasting brands and images of the product (image making), for example:

UA *LG – світ одним дотиком* / EN (lit.) LG - the world with one touch.

UA *Корона – символ благородного смаку* / EN (lit.) Crown is a symbol of noble taste.

(ii) Retail advertising – this type of advertising focuses on market demand and delivery of the needed to the target consumers, in particular:

UA *Наталі – розумний підхід до життя* / EN (lit.) Natalie: a smart approach to life

UA *Сампер – прогулянка з фантазією* / EN (lit.) Camper: a walk with fantasy.

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- (iii) Business advertising – business advertising is carried out by one type of business for the others:
 UA *Life – життя прекрасне* / EN (lit.) Life: life is beautiful.
 UA *Cleaning – зробимо життя чистішим* / EN (lit.) Cleaning: let's make life cleaner.
- (iv) Political advertising is used by politicians to influence their voters in order to achieve personal goals.
- (v) Direct advertising – a kind of advertising that aims at specific consumers and specific planning:
 UA *Росинка – насолода у кожній краплі* / EN (lit.) Dewdrop: pleasure in every drop.
 UA *Armani Code – секретний код жінки* / EN (lit.) Armani Code: the secret code of a woman.
- (vi) Institutional (corporate) advertising – advertising, which determines the creation of corporate identity to achieve organizational goals and objectives, for example:
 UA *Укрсиббанк – зірки до ваших послуг* / EN (lit.) Ukrsibbank: stars at your service
 UA *Правексбанк – традиції і сучасність, ми беремо краще від них* / EN (lit.) Pravexbank: traditions and modernity, we take the better from them.
- In general, it is facilitated that advertising is a multifunctional field that serves the owners to achieve many goals. Advertising is a various form of impersonal imagination and presentation of ideas, goods or services on behalf of an outstanding sponsor (see Table 1).

Table 1. Means of advertising distribution

Advertising in the press	newspapers, magazines
Printed advertising	catalogs, directories, leaflets, newsletters, press releases
Advertising by means of notice	radio, television, cable TV
Mail advertising	direct mail brochures, catalogs, video discs
Outdoor advertising	posters, big boards
Film and video advertising	film and video film, slide films
Advertising on transport	inscriptions on transport, stickers
Advertising in places of sale	show-window, packing
Advertising on the Internet	banners, mailing
Advertising digita	hypertexts
Other	fairs, seminars, souvenirs, discounts, etc

The text of the advertisement, like another product of human activity, reflects the subject of activity, the author's "I", which permeates the entire linguistic fabric of the text.

Odintsov (1980) considers the advertising text in two ways: first, a characteristic feature of this text; second, as an individual manifestation of the personality in connection with a particular advertiser in the construction of the text [19, p. 45].

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF ADVERTISING TEXT

The language of advertising develops on the basis of all known functional styles. Baranov (2013), Soloshenko (1990), Selivanova (2008), Lukin (2015) and other researchers underline that elements of different styles are often successfully used in advertising texts. It is relevant to follow the use of conversational style in more detail. Thus, the main requirements that the text must meet are as follows:

1. Advertising text must be specific, targeted. It is necessary to allocate those features, which favorably distinguish the advertised object from others from a number of similar.
2. Advertising should avoid distractions. Even if it is necessary to put forward a certain general position, it should be confirmed by facts and explained by concrete examples.
3. The language of the text is characterized from the standpoint of three main aspects: lexical, morphological and syntactic. To this end, it is important to analyse the mentioned three aspects of the text.

The lexical resources of the advertising text include linguistic and extralinguistic factors. The most common lexical characteristics to consider are the following:

- Word length,
- The ratio of specific (abstract) words. Concrete words are easier to remember than the abstract ones,
- Correlation of uncoded and coded words: advertising appeal is directed to a specialized (professional) or general audience;
- Words with a high frequency of usage: the more often words are used, the easier they are perceived.

Morphological characteristics depend on a number of factors:

- 1) The total number of affixes,
- 2) Use of personal pronouns,

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3) The number of verbs.

A particularly important point is the number of verbs. Verbs symbolize specific actions to which the consumer is called upon – so called call to action, for example:

UA *Life – купуйте та отримуйте теплі подарунки* / EN (lit.) Life - buy and receive warm gifts.

It is found that the more verbs are used in the advertising text in the Ukrainian and other languages, the better it is perceived.

Syntactic characteristics depend on two factors, namely:

- 1) Sentence length,
- 2) Sentence structure.

The length of syntactic units is determined by the total number of words in the sentence, and the average length of the sentence. The sentence structure consists of the total number of simple sentences and additions to the basic structural scheme.

The characteristics of the consumer also affect the relationship of clarity and ambiguity, which is perceived by the text of the advertising message.

The above characteristics can be grouped in two directions - motivation to read and reading skills. Reader interest is the tendency to voluntarily look for materials to read advertising text and spend time on it. The other characteristic reflects the socio-cultural and general language, educational level of the consumer.

Katerniuk (2006) identifies several basic skills for processing advertising texts:

- Knowledge of the meaning of properties,
- The ability to choose the correct meaning of a word or statement depending on the context,
- Necessity to follow the development of this text,
- Highlight of the main idea in the text,
- Answers to questions that stand out in the advertising text,
- Distinguishment between stylistic devices used in the text [10, p. 36].

Therefore, it is crucial that consumers understand the idea behind the ad text. The value of ad text for advertising is very important. It is thanks to the understanding of the advertising message that the idea that the manufacturer of a certain product wanted to convey to the consumer is realized. According to Odintsov (1980) the language of advertising texts should inform and persuade, be correct, specific and logical. From the linguistic point of view, advertising is “a special sphere of practical activity, the product of which are verbal works - advertising texts” [19, p. 14].

Advertising messages are now among the most aggressive types of language products, because to achieve a purely pragmatic goal - to meet demand for certain products, advertisers use the latest knowledge in neuro- and psycholinguistics, social psychology, consciously involving the entire language arsenal (lexical, phraseological, syntactic, spelling, stylistic means) to influence the word on the mass consumer. Zirka (2004) states that this should be a pseudo-objective, virtual reality - a myth in which it is planned to involve the consumer [32, p. 134]; a world that appears in a much simplified or distorted form.

It is no wonder why the structure of the advertising text deserves attention. It is the most important element of advertising. The text of the advertising message will be successful with readers provided the optimal structure. It is identified that traditionally, the composition of advertising text consists of the following blocks:

- a) Slogan (cliché) - a short advertising headline, motto, logo,
- b) Strings - the text that carries the idea of the advertising message,
- c) Information block - the main text, which provides important arguments,
- d) Final part,
- e) Additional information: address, contact phone number, email, etc.

The task of such distribution of material is to attract the attention of readers, to encourage them to read the text of the advertising appeal. The slogan reflects the company's philosophy, its corporate policy in various fields. This is essentially the title of the message and the first lines of text.

The title of the advertising text is an important verbal part. It usually expresses the main advertising appeals. The most important functions of the title are as below:

- To attract attention → ATTRACT in inbound marketing,
- To interest the consumer → APPEAL in digital marketing,
- To encourage the desire to buy goods → CONVERT and DELIGHT as known in the inbound.

Gerasimenko (2016) argues that producing a product name that would attract recipients “by associating the object of advertising with belonging to a particular social group that has authority in the minds of potential consumers” is the most significant marketing strategy [7, p. 36]. Muzykant (1998) comments the main requirements for the slogan are the ability to remember, the present name of the main brand, easy translation into other [18, p. 18], for example:

UA *Toyota – керуй мрією* / EN (lit.) Toyota - control your dream

UA *МТС: про кого ти думаєш зараз?* / EN (lit.) MTS: Who are you thinking about?

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It is revealed that in order to reduce the degree of social tension in the process of using advertising as a means of language influence (language aggression, manipulation and suggestion), certain hidden pragmatic techniques are used.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, advertising slogan is a communicative message that has a pragmatic instruction to convey true information about the subject of advertising to the largest number of people in order to encourage them to take action - to use and purchase the advertised product. The slogan is focused primarily on achieving the maximum pragmatic effect: to present the brand, distribute the advertised products, actually sell the product, and even forcibly impose it on a potential consumer.

Therefore, the following aspects are clearly combined, which logically represent the advertising text as a non-standard object of linguistic description in the polylingual cultures:

1) Polylingual components:

- introduction into the advertising message of linguistic facts by different types of fonts,
- a combination of natural and unnatural semiotic systems (signs, drawings, symbols),
- introduction to the text of visuals;

2) Multicultural and/or polycultural components.

The focus of advertising appeals to the consumer primarily on the creation and consolidation in the minds of consumers of the necessary image of the product and the resulting primary attention to the associative-constitutive possibilities of words often leads to "darkening" their semantics, simplification of nominative meanings and increased use of discursive pragmas.

Since man is the main anthropocentric component of a society, interacts in it within the framework of active multicultural / polycultural and polylingual life, the specifics of the pragmatics of advertising lies with the production of advertising text and visual information to it, distribution and reproduction of advertising slogans, marketing strategies, tactics, etc. - various influencing linguistic and cultural factors. The functioning and perception of the advertising slogan as part of advertising and part of a particular national culture is inconceivable without taking into account the socio-cultural and multicultural context, which reveals the peculiarities of this society due to the specifics of mental development, history, conditions and other national factors.

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